

TRUMP'S RECIPROCAL TARIFF POLICY: ECONOMIC-POLITICAL ANALYSIS AND ITS IMPLICATIONS FOR INDONESIA

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***Abstract:** The reciprocal tariff policy implemented by the Donald Trump administration marked the resurgence of protectionism in the global trade system. This study analyzes the policy using the International Political Economy (IPE) approach, specifically the mercantilism perspective, to explain how the policy reflects the state's strategy in securing domestic economic interests. Through literature study and analysis of various international responses, particularly from Indonesia, this research shows that the reciprocal tariff policy has a broad impact on the global trade order. For Indonesia, this policy triggers strategic challenges in maintaining national economic stability, but also opens opportunities to strengthen its bargaining position in international trade forums and encourage more active economic diplomacy. The findings of this research demonstrate the importance of developing countries like Indonesia to formulate adaptive strategies in facing the ever-changing global political-economic dynamics.*

Keywords: reciprocal tariff, protectionism, international political economy, Trump, global trade

Introduction

International Political Economy (IPE) is used as an interdisciplinary study that plays an important role in understanding the dynamics of relations between countries in the era of globalization. IPE is a study that examines the relationship between politics and economics at the international level which helps explain how economic forces influence political policies and vice versa. IPE analysis highlights the role of key actors, such as countries, multinational corporations, and international organizations in shaping global dynamics. Since the beginning of the 20th century, IPE studies have developed with various theoretical approaches, including realism, liberalism, and constructivism, each of which provides a different perspective in analyzing global political economy phenomena (Bakry, 2015).

Regarding the role of the state,, Nugroho (2022) emphasizes that the government's role is not only limited to managing power efficiently but also includes providing services that have a real impact on society. In the face of the Trump era reciprocal tariff policy which created an international trade order, developing countries like Indonesia need to adopt a strategic position

to maintain their national interests. This illustrates how important the function of the state is in facing global challenges through the implementation of responsive, structured economic and political policies that can improve people's welfare.

Over the past two decades, the international trade system has experienced significant changes marked by the emergence of new protectionism policies. This shift marks the end of the era of free trade which has been the main pillar of the global economic system after the Cold War. Major countries, especially the United States which was previously known as the main promoter of trade liberalization, have begun to shift their policy orientation towards protecting domestic interests. This phenomenon became even more apparent with the election of Donald Trump as President of the United States in 2016, which marked a drastic change in the foreign policy and global economic approach of the United States (Yanuarti et al., 2020).

The most prominent international trade policy of the Trump administration was the implementation of reciprocal tariffs, namely the imposition of trade tariffs on trading partner countries that are considered to have harmed the economic interests of the United States. This approach reflects a protectionism paradigm characterized by an emphasis on the "America First" principle, and directly triggered tensions in the multilateral trade system that has been running under the auspices of the World Trade Organization (WTO). Trump's policy shows a rejection of dependence on multilateral institutions and encourages bilateral negotiations which are considered more unilaterally beneficial for the United States (Bakry, 2015).

In IPE Theory, Trump's reciprocal tariff policy is understood through the perspective of mercantilism or economic nationalism. As explained by Umar Suryadi Bakry in his book *International Political Economy*, the new protectionism policy was born from the dissatisfaction of developed countries with the free trade system which is considered to no longer provide competitive advantages. The mercantilism school emphasizes the importance of state intervention in the economy to protect domestic industries and promote national interests. This approach is clearly seen in Trump's trade policy which tends to prioritize the economic interests of the United States, such as the application of high tariffs on imported goods and renegotiation of trade agreements. By adopting mercantilist principles, Trump sought to reduce the trade deficit and protect jobs at home, reflecting how economic ideology can influence foreign policy (Bakry, 2015).

Trump's tariff policy exacerbated global trade tensions, which then developed into a trade war between the United States and China. This trade war not only impacted the economic growth of the two countries, but also narrowed the space for other countries in the global supply chain. These reciprocal tariffs not only impact major trading partners such as China, but also

have spillover effects on developing countries such as Indonesia. In the journal *The Economic-Political Power of China After COVID-19*, it is explained that the reciprocal policies imposed by the US on China are one of the main drivers of changes in the structure of global economic interdependence, which ultimately affects the economic stability of developing countries, including Indonesia (Saragih et al., 2022).

Indonesia, as a developing country that is part of ASEAN, feels the impact of changes in global trade dynamics. In the context of economic-political rivalry between the United States and China, Indonesia is trapped in a complex strategic situation. Indonesia is required to maintain a balance between economic openness and national independence, as well as ensure the stability of the Indo-Pacific region amidst constantly changing global dynamics. Uncertainty in global trade relations, especially due to the trade war between the United States and China, opens up opportunities and challenges for Indonesia in maintaining national economic stability and its position in the global trade system (Yanuarti et al., 2020).

In the era of globalization and digitalization of contemporary international relations, foreign policy has gone beyond the limits of formal interaction between countries and now utilizes digital communication platforms as an integral component of strategic diplomacy. Wangke (2020) emphasizes that digital diplomacy has become a crucial instrument for shaping global perceptions, providing instant responses to international developments, and increasing a country's diplomatic effectiveness. The reciprocal tariff policy implemented by the Trump administration not only represents an economic challenge, but also presents a challenge to Indonesia's communication capabilities and diplomatic response in maintaining its strategic position and securing its national interests in global trade.

The concept of borderscapes and biopolitics explained in the journal on Indonesian border immigration confirms that global economic-political policies such as reciprocal tariffs also have a micro dimension, namely how their impact is felt in peripheral and vulnerable areas, such as border areas. This adds complexity in formulating a holistic national policy response to global dynamics (Ariato et al., 2022).

Trump's reciprocal tariff policy through the IPE lens is very important to analyze Indonesia's position and response in facing changing global dynamics. Large countries such as the United States have a significant influence in shaping international norms and policies, which can be analyzed through the IPE lens. Therefore, understanding IPE is very important to analyze the foreign policies of large countries, because the decisions taken are often influenced by economic considerations and strategic interests (Bakry, 2015).

From the explanation above, it explains that the study of Trump's reciprocal tariff policy is seen to understand the follow-up impact on Indonesia's position in the global trade system and its implications for foreign policy. This research aims to analyze how the reciprocal tariff policy implemented by the Trump administration affects the dynamics of economic-political relations, and how Indonesia as a developing country formulates strategies and policies to face challenges and take advantage of opportunities arising from these changes.

Research method

This research uses a qualitative approach with a library research method. The data sources used are secondary literature consisting of books, scientific journals, policy articles, and official documents relevant to the topic of reciprocal tariff policies implemented by the Donald Trump administration.

The analysis was carried out using the theoretical framework of International Political Economy (IPE), specifically through the perspectives of mercantilism and realism. This approach is used to explain how United States economic policy is not solely influenced by market interests, but also by strategic considerations and state power in the global trade system. The main focus of the analysis is directed at identifying the impact of the policy on Indonesia's position in international trade, as well as the response strategies taken by the Indonesian government.

Discussion

1. International Political Economy Approach Explains Reciprocal Tariff Policy

The international political economy approach offers a comprehensive analytical framework for understanding Trump's reciprocal tariff policy. Through the perspective of mercantilism or economic nationalism, this policy can be seen as a manifestation of the state's priority in securing domestic economic interests amidst global dynamics. In this paradigm, the state acts as a central actor that actively intervenes in market mechanisms to ensure national economic superiority and strategic security (Bakry, 2015).

Trump's policy demonstrates strong mercantilist characteristics with a focus on reducing trade deficits and protecting domestic industries through tariff instruments. The rejection of multilateralism and preference for bilateral negotiations reflects the United States' efforts to maximize unilateral gains and reduce dependence on the global trade system, which is considered detrimental to national interests (Bakry, 2015).

The realist paradigm in international political economy, as put forward by Robert Gilpin, emphasizes the interaction between political power and economic wealth. In this context, reciprocal tariff policy is not merely an economic policy, but also an instrument of the United States' power projection in the international system. The "America First" approach reflects the prioritization of national interests above established global trade norms (Bakry, 2015).

Research conducted by Sukri (2025) shows that the United States' reciprocal tariff policy is driven by several political factors, such as the protection of domestic industries aimed at protecting domestic industries from international competition through the application of lower tariffs compared to other countries, the existence of trade diplomacy used as a tool to pressure other countries to open their markets to American products, and geopolitical strategies to strengthen global influence and suppress countries that are considered a threat to its interests. This journal also shows that reciprocal tariff policies have a comprehensive impact on the global economy, such as changes in global trade flows that show how the US is trying to divert imports from high-tariff countries to low-tariff countries, rising prices of goods in importing countries due to the application of higher tariffs which results in changes in production patterns in exporting countries that are trying to shift production to products that are more competitive in the international market. The Implications of This Policy on Indonesia's Position in Global Trade.

Tariff increases not only affect market prices, but also the structure of global trade networks, as shown in an article written by Pina (2025) which shows that tariffs can have multidimensional impacts, namely eliminating targeted imports, diverting trade flows to third markets, exposing domestic companies to stronger foreign competition abroad, reducing consumer welfare, and ultimately harming the country that implements them. The international political economy approach in this article is seen from the recognition that trade policy is not only driven by economic factors, but also political factors, where tariffs can be used as a political tool to protect domestic industries, conduct trade diplomacy, and achieve geopolitical goals.

2. Implications of Reciprocal Tariff Policy on Indonesia's Position in Global Trade

Trump's reciprocal tariff policy creates multidimensional implications for Indonesia's position in the global trade architecture. At the macro level, the trade war between the United States and China triggered by this policy has resulted in market uncertainty and disruption in the global value chain, in which Indonesia is integrated as an important link. This instability

requires Indonesia to recalibrate its trade strategy to secure national economic interests. In geopolitics, Indonesia faces a strategic challenge to position itself in the midst of the rivalry of two dominant economic powers. Trump's Free and Open Indo-Pacific (FOIP) initiative presents a new economic-political dimension in the region that requires a strategic response from Indonesia. Through the ASEAN Outlook on the Indo-Pacific (AOIP), Indonesia seeks to build an inclusive approach that emphasizes multilateralism as an alternative to the polarization of major powers (Yanuarti et al., 2020).

At the micro level, changing global trade dynamics affect specific economic sectors and Indonesian border regions. The borderscapes perspective shows that global economic policies have real implications for peripheral spaces, requiring a policy approach that not only focuses on macroeconomic impacts but also considers the spatial and social dimensions of global trade changes (Ariato et al., 2022).

Research conducted by Sulaiman & Teresia (2025) states that regarding a policy regarding the United States' reciprocal tariffs which imposed a 32% tariff on Indonesian exports, the Indonesian government took a strategic approach by sending a high-level delegation led by Coordinating Minister for Economic Affairs Airlangga Hartarto and Minister of Finance Sri Mulyani Indrawati offering an increase in imports of American goods worth \$18-19 billion. This strategy is designed not only to reduce the US trade deficit with Indonesia, but also to open up investment opportunities in strategic sectors such as oil, gas and information technology. The implications of this policy on Indonesia's position in global trade include strengthening its bargaining position in international trade negotiation forums, diversifying trade relations which reduces dependence on a single market, and creating more balanced and mutually beneficial economic relations with major trading partners, especially the United States.

This is in line with what Christina (2025) wrote. The US 32% tariff policy on Indonesian exports has had a serious impact on the palm oil industry, prompting SPKS (small farmers group) to urge the elimination of export taxes worth \$196 per metric ton to offset the 3% price decline, while GAPKI proposed a reduction in export costs of \$100 per ton specifically to the US to maintain competitiveness against Malaysia. This illustrates how reciprocal tariff policies not only put pressure on prices at the farmer level but also force Indonesia to adjust its export tax policies to remain competitive in the global market, making the response to these tariffs a determining factor in positioning Indonesia in international palm oil trade and maintaining the economic stability of local farmers.

It has been conveyed by the Chairman of the National Economic Council, Luhut Binsar Pandjaitan in his presentation, stating that the US reciprocal tariffs on Indonesia actually open up opportunities for repositioning in global trade and attracting foreign investment as a production base. Although high, the 32% tariff imposed by the US is still lower than other Southeast Asian countries such as Malaysia and Cambodia. The government responded with a deregulation policy to cut economic costs and increase the competitiveness of Indonesian products in the global market, with the hope of strengthening its position in the global supply chain and taking advantage of opportunities from cooperation with the European Union and BRICS countries (Alatas, 2025).

Conclusion

The protectionism paradigm in the global trade system has re-emerged through Trump's reciprocal tariff policy. When viewed from an international political economy approach, particularly the perspective of mercantilism, this policy reflects a state strategy to secure national interests through economics. The "America First" principle affirms how economic policy is utilized as a political tool to achieve international strategic goals.

The implications of this policy go beyond US-China tensions, creating challenges for developing countries like Indonesia, which must navigate global market uncertainty and maintain economic stability amidst disruptions to the world's supply chains. However, this situation also opens up diplomatic and strategic opportunities for Indonesia to strengthen its bargaining position in global trade. Indonesia is responding actively through economic diplomacy, trade review strategies, and fiscal policies such as export incentives and deregulation. The AOIP approach is also being utilized to maintain regional balance amidst the competition of major powers in the Indo-Pacific. Trump's reciprocal tariff policy is an important case in understanding the dynamics of contemporary international relations, which demonstrates the close link between politics and economics. For Indonesia, this challenge has the potential to be a catalyst for strengthening economic resilience, expanding trade networks, and positioning itself as an actor in the transforming global political economy.

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